

ESTIMATION OF ALIPHATIC THIOCARBAMIDES. PART II. N-METHYLTHIOCARBAMIDES

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The method for the determination of thiocarbamide with iodine and sodium bicarbonate, described earlier, has been extended to the determination of *N*-methyl-, *N*:*N*-dimethyl-, *N*:*N'*-dimethyl-, *N*:*N*:*N'*-trimethyl- and *N*:*N*:*N'*:*N'*-tetramethyl- thiocarbamides.

As compared to the large amount of work reported on thiocarbamide, the derivatives and homologues of thiocarbamide seem to have received little attention. Wöjahn (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1951, 284, 243) reported iodimetric estimation of tetramethylthiocarbamide by Werner's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 1; 1912, 101, 2166). Sahasrabudhey and Singh (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 223) extended Werner's method and the Williams' mercurous nitrate method (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1939, 117, 91) to the estimation of certain *N*-substituted methylthiocarbamides. The iodimetric method suffers from the limitation that the end points are not sharp and as the reaction involving the formation of formamidine disulphide is reversible, considerable dilution is necessary for its quantitative completion. The degree of dilution required besides being large is different with different compounds.

In an earlier communication (*this Journal*, 1960, 37, 213) the author has shown that iodine in weakly alkaline media oxidises thiocarbamide quantitatively to carbamide and sulphate. The estimation of thiocarbamide is accurate over a wide range of concentrations and experimental conditions (*loc. cit.*). The method has now been extended to the quantitative determination of *N*-methyl-, *N*:*N*-dimethyl-, *N*:*N'*-dimethyl-, *N*:*N*:*N'*-trimethyl- and *N*:*N*:*N'*:*N'*-tetramethyl- thiocarbamides.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure followed for the visual titrimetric method as well as the potentiometric method was essentially the same as described earlier (*loc. cit.*). Titrations were also carried out by taking an excess of iodine, adding to it a measured volume of the required methylthiocarbamide solution, and back-titrating the excess iodine against a standard arsenious oxide solution.

The various *N*-substituted methylthiocarbamides were prepared in the laboratory and purified by double crystallisation from water or water-ethanol mixtures. M.p.s were checked with literature data.

N-Monomethylthiocarbamide was prepared by Hofmann's method from ethanolic ammonia and methyl isothiocyanate (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1869, 17, 72). The crude product after suitable purification and recrystallisation melted at 119° [lit. m.p. 117-18° (Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 517); 118° (Andreash, *Monatsh.*, 1881, 2, 277; Dyson and Hunter, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1926, 45, 421); 119-20° (Salkowskii, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 2724)].

N:*N*-Dimethylthiocarbamide was prepared according to the procedure of Wallach (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1874) by the condensation of dimethylcyanamide with H₂S. After several recrystalli-

sations and decolorisation with animal charcoal, a colorless pure sample was obtained, m.p. 162° [lit. m.p. : 158-59° (Wallach, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1873); 159° (Salkowskii, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2505); 161° (Singh and Sakia, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 695)].

N : N'-*Dimethylthiocarbamide* was prepared by Hofmann's method (*loc. cit.*) by the condensation of methyl isothiocyanate and methylamine. The crude product obtained was a semisolid one, but on further purification it yielded only a syrupy liquid. Any attempt to purify it further resulted in its decomposition and a significant loss of the material.

N : N : N'-*Trimethylthiocarbamide* was prepared by the condensation of methyl isothiocyanate and dimethylamine (Hofmann, *loc. cit.*). The crude product after two recrystallisations melted at 87° [lit. m.p. : 86-87° (Lecher and Gubernator, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1087); 87° (Singh, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 610)].

N : N : N' : N'-*Tetramethylthiocarbamide* was obtained by thermal decomposition of tetramethylthiuram disulphide (Bloomfield, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1946, 1, 316) as recommended by Sahasrabudhey (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 341). On repeated crystallisation from water a colorless, pure product was obtained melting at 78° (Sahasrabudhey, *loc. cit.*; Delépine, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1910, iv, 7, 989; Schenck, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1912, 77, 370).

TABLE I

Iodimetric estimation of N-methylthiocarbamides with bicarbonate buffer.

(End point observed visually).

Conc. of methyl thio- carbamide soln.	Conc. of I ₂ -soln. (20 c.c. taken).	10% NaHCO ₃ soln. added.	Methylthiocarbamide		
			Equiv. vol.	Found.	
A. Monomethylthiocarbamide.					
0.7000 g./litre	0.1036 N	30.0 c.c.	33.40 c.c.	0.6992 g./litre	99.88%
1.4000	"	30.0	16.70	1.3984	99.88
B. Unsym.-dimethylthiocarbamide.					
0.9828	0.1036	40.0	27.45	0.9828	100.00
1.6624	"	25.0	16.20	1.6650	100.15
C. Sym.-dimethylthiocarbamide.					
1.4800	0.1036	40.0	19.25	1.4020	94.71
2.4268	"	40.0	12.65	2.1330	87.90
D. Trimethylthiocarbamide.					
1.0540	0.1036	40.0	29.00	1.0580	100.30
2.1080	"	30.0	14.55	2.1090	100.00
E. Tetramethylthiocarbamide.					
1.0568	0.1026	30.0 (+5 g. KI)	42.90	1.0540	99.70
2.2840	"	30.0 (+5 g. KI)	19.80	2.2830	99.90

TABLE II

Direct potentiometric titrations of iodine and N-substituted methylthiocarbamides.

[0.1036 N-iodine taken (10 c.c.) for each experiment].

Me.-thio. present	10% NaHCO ₃ soln. added.	Methylthiocarbamide.		
		Vol. reqd.	Found.	
A. N-Monomethylthiocarbamide.				
1.400 g./litre	5.0 c.c.	8.40 c.c.	1.3900 g./litre	99.29%
"	20.0	8.40	"	"
"	50.0	8.40	"	"
0.7000	10.0	16.70	0.6992	99.88
B. N:N-Dimethylthiocarbamide				
1.6624	5.0	8.20	1.6452	98.97
"	20.0	8.20	"	"
"	50.0	8.20	"	"
0.9828	10.0	13.80	0.9776	99.47
C. N:N'-Dimethylthiocarbamide.				
1.4800	10.0	9.70	1.3908	93.97
"	20.0	9.70	"	"
2.4268	10.0	6.40	2.1080	86.89
"	20.0	6.40	"	"
D. N:N':N'-Trimethylthiocarbamide.				
2.1080	10.0	7.30	2.0968	99.47
"	40.0	7.30	"	"
1.0540	10.0	14.60	1.0484	"

TABLE III

N : N : N' : N'-Tetramethylthiocarbamide.

[0.1026 N-Iodine* = 10 c.c. taken for each experiment. T.M.T. present = 2.284 g./litre].

10% NaHCO ₃ soln. added.	Vol. of T.M.T. required.	T.M.T. found.		Remarks (amount of solid KI added).
15.0 c.c.	9.50 c.c.	1 g.
15.0	9.60	2
15.0	9.80	2.3072 g./litre	101.01%	3
15.0	9.90	2.2840	100.00	5
15.0	9.90	"	"	10

* Iodine solution contained potassium iodide four times by weight of iodine

TABLE IV

Back titrations of excess iodine against arsenious oxide.*

Thiocarbamide.	Methylthiocarbamide.		Percentage.
	Present	Found	
A. Monomethyl	1.4000 g./litre 0.7000	1.3930 g./litre 0.6965	99.51 % "
B. Unsym.-dimethyl	1.6624 0.9828	1.6570 0.9789	99.79 99.60
C. Sym.-dimethyl	1.4800 2.4268	1.4050 2.1314	94.88 87.83
D. Trimethyl	2.1080 1.0540 "	2.1138 1.0390 1.0560	100.28 98.51 100.20
E. Tetramethyl	1.0568 2.2840	1.068 2.292	101.06 100.60

* For details of procedure see this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 213.

TABLE V

Sulphate estimation in the reaction mixture.

In each case 50 c.c. iodine + 100 c.c. of 10% sod. bicarbonate were taken.

Conc. of I ₂ soln.	Thiocarbamide soln. required	Conc. of thiocarbamide soln.	BaSO ₄		Thiocarbamide found.
			Found.	Calc.	
A. Monomethylthiocarbamide.					
0.1036 N	41.6 c.c.	1.4000 g./litre	0.1495 g.	0.1511 g.	99.42%
0.1115	44.8	1.4000	0.1618	0.1628	99.42
B. Unsym.-dimethylthiocarbamide.					
0.1036	40.5	1.6624	0.1499	0.1511	99.22
0.1115	43.6	1.6624	0.1620	0.1628	99.51
C. Sym.-dimethylthiocarbamide.					
0.1036	48.1 (45.5)*	1.4800	0.1512	0.1673 (0.1511)*	90.38 100.1
0.1115	31.6 (29.86)*	2.4268	0.1627	0.1722 (0.1628)*	94.91 99.93
D. Trimethylthiocarbamide.					
0.1036	36.3	2.1080	0.1499	0.1511	99.22
0.1115	39.0	2.1080	0.1619	0.1628	99.49

* Calculated on the basis of analytical results obtained and assuming the sym.-dimethylthiocarbamide to be 94.7% pure.

DISCUSSION

Tables I and II show that the *N*-monomethyl-, *N*:*N*-dimethyl-, *N*:*N'*-dimethyl-, and *N*:*N*:*N'*-trimethyl-thiocarbamides are quantitatively oxidised by iodine in presence of sodium bicarbonate buffer. The change appears to be analogous to that with thiocarbamide.

(where R is a methyl group or a hydrogen atom).

A freshly prepared 10% solution of sodium bicarbonate, free from any contamination with sodium carbonate, was used. The amount of bicarbonate taken was in such excess that the reaction mixture remained always alkaline after the reaction was complete. The titrations were performed by observing the end point visually in the usual manner (Table I) and potentiometrically (Table II). Back-titrations with excess iodine against arsenious oxide were also carried out (Table IV).

The results confirm the above equation except in the case of sym. -(N:N')-dimethylthiocarbamide (Tables I, II and IV) for which the experimental values are near about 87% of that expected. The best results obtained are about 94% of the actual amount taken. This is undoubtedly on account of some inseparable impurities present in the sample of this compound which could not be purified by crystallisation. This compound has been obtained in a syrupy state by several previous workers (Andreash, *loc. cit.*; Singh, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 355) while several other workers claim to have obtained it in the solid state and have reported different melting points, viz., 49-50° (Salkowski, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 2724); 51.5° (Hecht, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 281); 51-52° (Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 328); 56-58° (Wilson and Woodger, *ibid.*, 1955, 2943) and 61° (Freund and Asbrand, *Annalen*, 1895, 285, 170). The sample used in the present case was a syrupy one.

Sulphate estimations were carried out in the reaction mixture by acidifying it at the end point with dilute hydrochloric acid, boiling for two minutes and precipitating barium sulphate as usual. The results presented in Table V confirm the assumption that the sulphur of the thiocarbamides is completely oxidised to the sulphate. The method therefore has the added advantage that volumetric and gravimetric procedures can be carried out with the sample in one operation.

When this procedure was applied to tetramethylthiocarbamide, a turbidity appeared in the solution, which could be avoided by the addition of an excess of potassium iodide (in addition to that present in the iodine solution used) prior to titration. Moreover, the stoichiometry in this case suggests that the oxidation does not proceed up to the stage of sulphate formation and only 3 molecules of iodine per molecule of T.M.T. are required. The results for tetramethyl thiocarbamide, reported in Tables I, III and IV, have been calculated on the basis of

which holds true only when a sufficient excess of potassium iodide is present. Back-titrations of excess iodine with arsenious oxide can be carried out as usual using visual or potentiometric end points in the same buffer medium, viz., sodium bicarbonate. Excess KI is required to be added as before. The actual nature of the oxidation product in this case and the role of potassium iodide are not yet clear and are being investigated.

The author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. S. S. Joshi, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., for his keen interest and help, and to Dr. R. H. Sahasrabudhey for his valuable criticism and suggestions.